

Motivation Relationship Work with Perilaku Caring Nurses in Emergency Care Facilities Hospital Priama Nawacita Comes Dave Mahakam Ulu

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ABSTRACT

Motivation is very closely linked to any action performed by a nurse in caring behavior. Nursing is a professional service, an integral part of home health care. The success of a hospital in carrying out its functions is characterized by the quality of service provided by the hospital. Objective: To find out the relationship between the motivation of work and the behavior of the nurse in the Emergency Care Facility of the Hospitals Priama Nawacita Datah Dave Mahakam Ulu. The research design on this study is observational using a cross-sectional approach. The research was conducted in February 2023. The population in this study is the whole of the nurses who work in the Emergency Care Facility of the Hospital Priama Nawacita Datah Dave Mahakam Ulu amounting to 20 people. Sample determination using total sampling. The statistical tests used are Chi Square. The results have been linked to the motivation of work with the behavior of nurses in the Emergency Care Facility of the Hospital Priama Nawacita Datah Dave Mahakam Ulu.

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is a process that comes from within a person who is shown to be energetic behavior (Ryan RM, 2000), and motivation is very closely related to any action performed by a nurse in caring behaviour. (Khodijah & Marni, 2014).

There are still many nurses who have not taken action with all their heart so the motivation of work plays an important role in determining the caring behavior of a nurse in serving the patient. This statement is supported by Purwaningsih, (2015) which states that to enhance caring behavior, a nurse requires an inward impulse called motivation.

Caring can generally be understood as an ability to be dedicated to others, vigilant surveillance, a sense of empathy towards others and a feeling of love or affection. In nursing, caring is an important core part especially in nursery practice (Morrison, 2009). Caring behavior involves the care of patients, families and individual patients and is also related to the satisfaction of nurses in their positions and professions (Longo J, 2009), and in the practice of nurse behaviors caring contains humanistic values, a responsive attitude, and responsibility to meet patient expectations.

Health workers like nurses are the key to success in achieving the goals of health development. Health energy contributes up to 80% to the success of development and good health care. (Menteri Kesehatan RI, 2011). Nursing is a professional service, an integral part of hospital health care. The success of a hospital in carrying out its functions is characterized by the quality of service provided by the hospital. Therefore, the healthcare industry needs a more skilled workforce as a result of advances in medical technology and demand for more sophisticated customer care. (Manurung, dkk, 2013).

Based on observations and interviews with 10 shift nurses in the morning and afternoon in the Emergency Care Facility, 40 percent of the nursing staff said they still had a passion for work, felt comfortable with the workplace atmosphere and good co-workers, while the remaining 60 percent were less enthusiastic. The reason the nurses are less enthusiastic is that some say that the division of services with the burden of work is less appropriate, some that the work burden is light but the share is the same, late receiving honor / salary, more and more heavy tasks but less getting attention from the leadership and management of the hospital.

The researchers also looked at the absence data at the hospital's Emergency Care Facilities, where Dave Mahakam Ulu came to visit, although the presence was always filled according to the schedules, but there were still many who did not arrive on time or late, for various reasons. The situation on the ground shows that the motivation of the nurse's work is still low, as evidenced by the lack of work passion, discipline, loyalty, responsibility. This condition will have a direct impact on the decrease in labor yields and performance so that the performance of nurses will result in a low quality of service. (Purwaningsih, 2015).

There is a high motivation in the person will encourage them to act and perform tasks well so that it will affect the productivity of work, also the opposite if the nurse is not underpinned by a strong desire and motivation of

work and good adjustment then in the performance of the job will not be good and optimal so will impact on the satisfaction of the work of nurses and will lead to compulsion so referring to the formation of bad caring behavior and work below standards (Gurusinga, 2013).

Based on observations and interviews conducted by researchers of 15 patients in the IGD on the behavior of caring nurses, the data were obtained that 5 caring nurse and 10 nurse are less caring with criteria such as less knowledge of patient needs, less assertive when listening to patient and family stories, less friendly when interacting with patients, not introducing themselves at the first meeting with patients and rarely providing information before taking action, less kind when explaining a question raised by patients.

If a nurse is not bound by a strong desire and motivation to work and good adjustment then in carrying out the work will not be good and optimal so will affect the satisfaction of the nurse and will lead to compulsion so referring to the formation of poor caring behavior and under the standards of work (Gurusinga, 2013).

In fact, there are still many nurses who are not caring for the patient, even nurses who do not have time to listen to the client, provide comfort and other caring actions. Sometimes nurses see the therapeutic relationship between a nurse and a client as something less important to pay attention to. Lack of caring behavior in IGD patients will have an impact on conditions such as discomfort or anxiety that will impede the patient's recovery.

Nurses carry out nursing care based on knowledge and advice aimed at individuals, families, and healthy or ill groups or communities. (UU Keperawatan no 38 tahun 2018). The nursing team must work in accordance with the standards that have been established in providing health care to the client. It is intended to ensure that the nursing services provided at all times are secure and able to meet the needs and expectations of both the quality and quantity of the care. (Liang, Chen Le, & Huang, 2012).

The behavior and attitude that a nurse should develop is one of the caring behaviors that can be developed in conducting evaluation, planning, implementation and evaluation in practice. (Williams, 2013). Caring behavior can bring changes for patients both physically, psychologically, spiritually and socially to a better direction.

Based on the above background, the author is interested in researching the relationship of motivation of work with the behavior of nurses in the Emergency Care Facility of the Hospital Priama Nawacita Datar Dave Mahakam Ulu.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Work Motivation

Work motivation is the desire to act. Everyone can be motivated by some different forces. Work motivation is the result of a set of internal and external forces that cause workers to choose the appropriate path of action and use certain behaviors. Work motivation generally relates to a purpose, whereas organizational aims cover work-related behaviour. (Wibowo, 2014).

Nurse Caring Behavior

Caring behavior as a form of caring, giving attention to others, being people-centred, respecting self-esteem, and humanity, a commitment to preventing deteriorating health status, paying attention and respecting others (Nursalam, 2014).

METHODOLOGY

The research design on this study is observational using a cross-sectional approach. The research was conducted in February 2023. The population in this study is the whole of the nurses who work in the Emergency Care Facility of the Hospital Priama Nawacita Datar Dave Mahakam Ulu amounting to 20 people. Sample determination using total sampling. The statistical bi-variation test used is Chi Square.

The instrument used in this study is a questionnaire that covers questions about job motivation and nursing behavior. The data obtained will be processed and the results will be displayed in a percentage of the frequency distribution table using the univariate analysis formula. Where univariate analysis is used to determine the characteristics of respondents as well as research variables. The data is then processed with the help of computerization using statistical tests. Where the bi-variation test in this study uses a chi square with a fertility limit of $\alpha=0,05$.

RESULTS

Univariat Analysis

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents of nurses in the Emergency Care Facility of the Hospitals of Pratama Nawacita Coming Dave Mahakam Ulu

No.	Karakteristik	Jumlah	
		Frekuensi (n=20)	%
1	Usia		
	Lansia Awal (46-50 tahun)	2	10
	Dewasa Akhir (36-45 tahun)	2	10
	Dewasa Awal (26-35 tahun)	16	80
2	Jenis Kelamin		
	Laki-laki	7	35
	Perempuan	13	65
3	Pendidikan		
	Strata 1	8	40
	Diploma III	12	60
4	Lama Bekerja		
	>10 tahun	4	20
	5-10 tahun	10	50
	<5 tahun	6	30

The results of the study on the characteristics of respondents by age category showed that most respondents were in the early age category (26-35 years) of 16 persons (80%), a small proportion of the respondents in the age category was in the late adult age category (36-45 years), 2 persons (10%) and

the older age category (46-50 years) 2 people (10%). Based on the gender category, the majority respondents with female gender were 13 (65%) and a minor proportion respondent with male gender was 7 (35%). According to the educational categories, the most educated respondents Diploma III was 12 persons (60%) and half of the educated Strata I was 8 persons (40%). On the basis of the long-term working category, it was shown that the most long-time respondents of 5-10 years of work were 10 persons (50%), almost half of those with a long term of work < 5 years were 6 persons (30%), and a small portion of those who had a long time of work > 10 years were 4 persons (20%).

Table 2. Motivation of nursing in the emergency care facility of the hospital Priama Nawacita comes Dave Mahakam Ulu

MotivasiKerja	Jumlah	
	F	%
Tinggi	5	25
Sedang	11	55
Rendah	4	20
Jumlah	20	100

The results of the study in table 4.2 on the motivation of nurses showed that the majority of respondents in the average motivation category were 11 (55%), and a small proportion of the high motivation categories were 5 (25%) and the low motivation group was 4 (20%).

Table 3. Behavior of nurses in the emergency care facility of the hospital Priama Nawacita comes Dave Mahakam Ulu

PerilakuCaringPerawat	Jumlah	
	F	%
Baik	5	25
Cukup	6	30
Kurang	9	45
Jumlah	20	100

The results of a study on nursing behavior in table 4.3 showed that almost half of the respondents had less than nine nurses (45%), a small proportion had more than six (30%) and a good 5 (25%) nursed behaviour.

Table 4. Relationship of work motivation with nurse caring behavior

MotivasiKerj a	Perilakucaringperawat								p-value
	Baik		Cukup		Kurang		Total		
	F	%	f	%	F	%	F	%	
Tinggi	5	25	0	0.0	0	0.0	5	25	0,00
Sedang	0	0.0	6	30	5	25	11	55	
Rendah	0	0.0	0	0.0	4	20	4	20	
Jumlah	5	25	6	30	9	45	20	100	

The results of the bivariate analysis based on table 4.4 on motivation for work with nurses caring behavior showed that almost half of the respondents were motivated for work of the highest category with good nursing behaviour category of 5 people (25%).

Based on the analysis performed using Chi Square, the value $p\text{value} = 0.00$ is less than the value $\alpha = 0.05$ or ($0,00 < 0.05$), which means there is a significant relationship between work motivation and nursing behavior.

DISCUSSION

The results of the bivariate analysis based on table 4.4 on motivation to work with nursing behavior of nurses in the Emergency Nursing Facility of the Nawacita Datar Dave Mahakam Ulu Hospital showed that the motivation for high-category work with the behaviour of good category nurses was 5 people (25%). Based on the analysis performed using the Chi Square test, the value $p\text{value} = 0.00$ is less than the value $\alpha = 0.05$ or ($0,00 < 0.05$), which means there is a significant relationship between work motivation and nursing behavior.

Yustina (2014) says that the individual motivation within a nurse can motivate a person to work harder so that they can their goals in caring behavior towards clients or carry out nursing care to the maximum. It increases the productivity of individual work that affects the organization's achievement especially in terms of serving the client so that the client is satisfied, also included in the factors that cause, channel, and maintain human behavior in the direction of a certain determination. (Nursalam, 2015).

Gibson, James, & John (2000) presented three concepts that influence caring behavior on a nurse's individual performance: Individual factors (capabilities and skills, background, and demographics), Psychological factors (attitude, personality, learning, and motivation) and Organizational factors (power sources, leadership style used by the head of the room, rewards earned, organizational structure used in the nursing room, and work model). It can be further detailed that the supporting elements of good nurse behaviour derive from the skills and motivations of a nurses, so that a nurser has good motivation requires the inward impetus of the nurse. The ability of an officer will be improved if he possesses extensive knowledge and has the skills to solve problems.

The researchers assume that each impulse that directs the behavior of nurses in the workplace is different so that the nurse in revealing the caring behaviour that he has to the client will also be different. Nurses are the most resource in the hospital, so to build a caring personality, the accused nurse must know the relationship between nursing and caring, and also supported by a good work motivation so influential to arouse, direct, and nurture caring conduct that is realized with love from within someone who is aimed in each doing an act to others.

Work motivation is essential for everyone, so that the caring behavior of the nurse towards the client is increasing especially in terms of the healing of the client. Without work motivation, work won't be able to go well.

A high-motivated nurse tends to provide good service, but if a nurse has a low or moderate work motivation, it makes the nurse lazy in doing the activity of serving and caring for the patient. An officer can perform his duties and duties to the maximum, because of the motivation that drives him to work with determination and discipline.

To create a qualified nurse requires encouragement from the hospital and from the nurse itself.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study have shown that there is a relationship between the motivation of work and the behavior of nurses in the Emergency Care Facility of Nawacita Datah Dave Mahakam Ulu Hospital (pvalue = 0,00).

To the health care provider Give the maximum service to the patient without looking at anything, re-enlarge the motivation and work spirit.

For the next researcher, do research on the behavior of nurses with different variables.

FURTHER STUDY

Do research on nursing behavior with different variables.

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